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GENNARO DI PRISCO, MASSIMO GIORGINI, PASQUALE CASCONI,
MICHELINA RUOCCO & EMILIO GUERRIERI

ASTER: A “PRIMA” PROJECT TO STUDY THE FUNCTIONAL
BIODIVERSITY IN TOMATO CROP

*ASTER: un progetto ‘Prima’ per studiare la biodiversità funzionale
in coltivazioni di pomodoro*

The aim of ASTER (Agroecology-inspired Strategies and Tools to Enhance Resilience and ecosystem services in tomato crop) is to build up a management model for small tomato producers of the Mediterranean Basin based on the application of main agroecology principles such as: (i) the protection (i.e. conservation) and the enhancement of functional biodiversity both above and belowground, to increase and exploit the ecosystem services (i.e. protection, nutrition, pollination) in alternative to the use of external synthetic inputs; (ii) the sustainable control of main pests and pathogens to reduce the environmental impact of plant protection practices; (iii) the circularity of the production chain to approach the “zero waste” objective. The model will improve the resilience of this fundamental crop in the economy of all Mediterranean Basin countries where it can be grown in open field or in protected systems, during the entire annual season, particularly in small farms. The results from this project will provide a model that can be extended to the sustainable production of other crops, in water-limited and non-water-limited socio-agro-ecosystems.

Authors’ Address — G. DI PRISCO, M. GIORGINI, P. CASCONI, M. RUOCCO, E. GUERRIERI – Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection – The Italian National Research Council (IPSP-CNR) Piazzale Enrico Fermi, 1 – 80055 Portici (Napoli, Italy); e-mail: gennaro.diprisco@ipsp.cnr.it

